

Viscometric, Light-scattering and Osmometric Studies of Viscose Solution. Part I

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From light-scattering data of concentrated (0.7%) and dilute (1%) viscose solutions, important conclusions have been drawn regarding the chemical nature of viscose solutions.

Viscose, a solution of cellulose xanthate, presents a complicated system and despite considerable fundamental studies, it has not yet been possible to successfully characterise it. Some workers suggest that xanthate formation is a micellar reaction¹ and according to others, it is a molecular reaction.²

Some investigations have recently been made by light-scattering technique to determine the molecular weight³, effect of ripening on molecular weight, size distribution, and other characteristics⁴ of viscose solution.

But many other important aspects of viscose solution, viz., the molecular or colloidal nature of dispersion, the gelation characteristics, etc., which could be satisfactorily studied by light scattering and other techniques, have not yet been pursued.

The present work was therefore undertaken to ascertain (i) the true chemical nature of viscose solution, (ii) the causes for unusual viscosity change during ripening, (iii) the relationship between change in viscosity and molecular weight, and (iv) the gel structure of viscose. In this communication we present data to illustrate the true chemical nature of viscose solutions only. For this purpose both concentrated and dilute solutions of viscose were prepared. The concentrated solution contained 6 to 7% cellulose and approached commercial viscose samples and the dilute solution contained 1% and less than 1% cellulose in the solution.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Xanthate.—Cellulose xanthate was prepared with filter paper (100% α -cellulose) and analytically pure NaOH and CS₂ by the standard procedure⁵.

Dispersion of Xanthate in NaOH Solution.—For Batches I and II, the cellulose xanthate was dispersed in 4% NaOH solution to obtain approximately 6.5% and 1.0%

1. Scherer *et al.*, *Rayon & Synthetic Textiles*, 1940, 30, 45.

2. Wynn, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1925, 17, 1044.

3. Tait *et al.*, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1951, 7, 261.

4. Onyon, *ibid.*, 1959, 37, 123.

5. Dorée, "The Methods of Cellulose Chemistry", Chapman and Hall Ltd., 1947, p. 261.

respectively. For Batch III, cellulose xanthate was dispersed in 4% NaOH solution to provide approximately 1.0% solution.

Ripening and Viscosity Measurement.—The viscose solutions, thus made, were kept in sealed conical flasks at a thermostatic bath, maintained at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$, for ripening. Viscosity was measured at regular intervals by a standard Ostwald viscometer, containing 25 ml of viscose solution (flow time, 4 to 5 seconds with respect to water) which was placed in the same bath, maintained at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$. Percentage of xanthate sulphur was determined by taking aliquot portions from the stoppered conical flasks at regular intervals.

Light-scattering Measurement.—For light-scattering measurement, the solution was centrifuged in a high-speed centrifuge at 16,000 to 18,000 r.p.m. to obtain an optically clear solution. This solution (30 ml) was taken in a rectangular optical cell, which was covered and sealed with cellophane tape, and then kept suspended in the bath, maintained at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$. The lateral scattering (I_{90}/I_0) of the solution was determined by removing the optical cell from the bath and placing it in the light-scattering photometer (Brice-Phoenix Universal Light-scattering photometer, series 1999-10) at wave length 548 μ . As the solution was coloured, blue light (436 μ) was not used. This was repeated till gelation set in. The lateral scattering of the solvent was similarly determined and deducted from that of the solution. After gelation had taken place, as determined by the steep rise in lateral scattering, the viscous mass was centrifuged at 16,000-18,000 r.p.m. The clear solution from the top of the centrifuge tube was taken in an optical cell and placed in the bath at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$. Its lateral scattering was then measured at regular intervals in the same way as before until second gelation set in, as evidenced by a second steep rise in the lateral scattering curve. The mass was again centrifuged and lateral scattering measured with gel-free, optically clear solution, as usual, till the next and the last gelation set in.

DISCUSSION

Regardless of the controversy as to the molecular or colloidal nature of dispersion of

cellulose xanthate in NaOH solution, it is highly probable that commercial viscose, in which concentration of cellulose (about 7%) is fairly high, is a mixture of micellar particles and molecular aggregates. Initially, when the viscose is prepared, the molecular aggregation may be very considerable, which accounts for the very high viscosity of viscose, and the fall of viscosity in the early stage may be ascribed to the gradual attaining of higher degree of dispersion and less degree of aggregation. This probably accounts for our observation (viscose Batch I, Fig. 1) made with a viscose solution of 6.5% cellulose concentration (very near to commercial viscose) that initially the viscosity falls in spite of the continuous decrease in the

percentage of xanthate sulphur and hence the number of xanthate groups. This can be contrasted with our observation, made in connection with the viscosity of the dilute viscose solutions containing 0.90% and 0.86% cellulose respectively, that viscosity does not really fall (Figs. 2 and 4) nor is there any marked decrease in the lateral

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

scattering (I_{90}/I_0) of the viscose solution (Figs. 3 & 5). On this basis, the dilute viscose solution should be closer to molecular rather than to micellar dispersion. This fact has

been amply substantiated by our observation that after gelation has set in, the insoluble, gel-containing larger and less xanthated cellulose molecules can be separated by high-speed centrifugation and the remaining clear viscose solution, containing smaller and more xanthated cellulose molecules, exhibits a lateral scattering which although much smaller than that of the original solution (Fig. 3, a-c) increases continuously until visible gelation again sets in. After this, the second gel may again be separated from the still smaller molecules which have not yet been completely dexanthated and which show increase in the lateral scattering in the usual way. This process of fractionation, which is possible only when the viscose solution is more or less in a molecular state of dispersion, cannot be done in the case of more concentrated solution (commercial viscose) where aggregates of large cellulose molecules, formed by hydrolysis and cross-linking, carry away the smaller and not-yet-dexanthated molecules, entrapped securely in the gel network.

FIG. 4

Again, comparing the I_{90}/I_0 vs. time plots (Fig. 3, a-c) for three fractions of the viscose (Batch II), it is seen that whereas I_{90}/I_0 values remain more or less steady before taking the upward swing in the case of original viscose solution (Fig. 3, a), those values for both the first and the second fraction (Fig. 3, b & c) take the upward turn even from the very beginning. This behaviour has again been observed in course of studies on viscose of Batch III (Fig. 5, b). This is probably due to the fact that the original viscose solution is not completely centrifuged and in all probability the tail portion of the original solution must have found its way into the next fraction of the viscose solution which is again under study. This is further supported by data for viscose of Batch III (Fig. 5, a and b).

CONCLUSION

From the study and analysis of data presented in Figs. 1 to 5, we tentatively arrive at the following conclusions:

(a) Commercial viscose containing about 7% cellulose is not a molecular dispersion. Most probably it is a colloidal solution.

(b) A dilute solution of viscose containing less than 1% of cellulose is in all probability very near to molecular dispersion. Its viscosity and lateral scattering support this conclusion.

FIG. 5

(c) That viscose solution even when highly diluted is polymolecular in nature is clearly demonstrated by its scattering behaviour. This fact can be taken advantage of in fractionation of cellulose molecules.